

**“ASSESSMENT OF METACOGNITION IN SUICIDAL PATIENTS:-
A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY”**

By

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DOCTOR OF MEDICINE

IN

PSYCHIATRY

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S.NO.	ABBREVIATION	FULL FORM
1.	MCQ	METACOGNITION
2.	BSIS	BECK'S SUICIDE INTENT SCALE
3.	BDI	BECK'S DEPRESSION INVENTORY
4.	BHI	BECK'S HOPELESSNESS INVENTORY
5.	NCRB	NATIONAL CRIME RECORDS BUREAU
6.	SDR	SUICIDE DEATH RATE
7.	DSH	DELEBRATE SELF HARM
8.	S- REF	SELF-REGULATORY EXECUTIVE FUNCTION
9.	CBT	COGNITIVE BEHAVIORAL THERAPY
10.	CAS	COGNITIVE-ATTENTIONAL SYNDROME
11.	OCD	OBCESSIVE COMPULSIVE DISORDER
12.	GAD	GENERALISED ANXIETY DISORDER
13.	TCQ	THOUGHT CONTROL QUESTIONNAIRE
14.	ESM	EXPERIENCE SAMPLING METHODOLOGY
15.	LCC	LACK OF COGNITIVE CONFIDENCE
16.	PBW	POSITIVE BELIEF ABOUT WORRY
17.	CSC	COGNITIVE SELF CONSCIOUSNESS
18.	NBUD	NEGATIVE BELIEFS ABOUT UNCONTROLLABILITY AND DANGER
19.	NCT	NEED TO CONTROL THOUGHTS
20.	MCT	METACOGNITIVE THERAPY

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Suicide rates in our country are alarming, with the highest among our productive age group, indicating that no efforts are effective in lowering them. There is a great challenge in treating a person's suicidal behavior because of little information available on what suicidal patients think about suicides. As metacognition is effective in framing metacognitive therapy in various other psychiatric illnesses, with few studies done globally and no clinical studies from India, it is important to understand the relationship between **metacognition and suicidal patients**. The purpose of this study is to learn more about the phenomenology of thinking about suicidal thoughts by studying metacognition in suicidal patients. Later, it aids in the development of a structured approach for psychiatrists and therapists to learn the thought process and plan effective treatment modalities in the near future, thereby preventing a large number of suicidal deaths that could be avoided with minimal effort.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: This cross-sectional study was carried out after taking institutional Ethical committee clearance of BLDE(DU) Shri B.M Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura. People in the age group of 18 to 60 years who have attempted suicide or having suicidal ideation, were clinically analyzed for any underlying psychiatric comorbidity and later suicidal intent, depression, hopelessness, and metacognition were evaluated using Beck's Suicide Intent scale (BSIS), Beck's Depression Inventory(BDI), Beck's Hopelessness Inventory (BHI) and Metacognition Questionnaire 30 (MCQ-30) respectively. Later the data was analyzed for understanding the metacognition underlying their attempted suicide.

RESULTS: A total of 115 subjects were included in the study, and the majority of the study population was 18-30 years old, with females forming 68% of the study population. Most of the subjects had suicidal ideation of less than one-month duration with low to medium intent of committing suicide and mild to moderate levels of depression and hopelessness. The study revealed that most subjects were experiencing family or financial stressors, which account for the reason for such thought processes. The study found that subjects' suicidal intent, depression, and

hopelessness were positively associated with higher metacognitive unhelpfulness; on closer examination, the metacognitive understanding revealed that negative beliefs about uncontrollability and danger, as well as the need to control thoughts, were the primary reasons they took the difficult decision to attempt suicide.

CONCLUSIONS: Metacognition plays a significant role in shaping cognitive processes, emotional regulation, and social beliefs that influence suicidal behaviors. Understanding the intricate interplay between metacognitive beliefs, cognitive therapies, emotional dysregulation, and environmental stressors is essential for developing effective interventions to prevent suicide and promote mental health. This study leads us to the conclusion that negative metacognition is the prevalent metacognitive thinking that affects a person's mental process through rumination, which exacerbates depression, heightens hopelessness, and ultimately strengthens the person's desire to commit suicide. Understanding metacognitive models of suicidal ideation in different populations is crucial for developing targeted interventions to prevent self-harm and suicide.

KEYWORDS: Metacognition, Suicide, Deliberate Self Harm, Metacognitive domains, Cognitive self-consciousness, Positive Beliefs about worry, Lack of Cognitive confidence, Need to control thoughts, Negative belief about worry.

1. INTRODUCTION

Every 40th second, a person dies by suicide somewhere in the world. Suicide kills approximately 800,000 people annually, accounting for about 1.4% of all deaths worldwide. As per National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) reports of 2020[1], Yearly, more than 100,000 people commit suicide in our country; there is an increased suicide rate per 100,000 of the total population from 6.3 in 1978 to 8.9 in 1990, rising to 11.25 between 2006 and 2011, finally stabilising around 10% between 2015 and 2019, and then rising back up to 11.3 in 2020. According to the reports, the majority of suicide cases were reported from Maharashtra, accounting for 13% of cases, followed by Tamil Nadu at 11%, Madhya Pradesh at 9.6%, and West Bengal at 8.6%, and Karnataka at 8%. The lowest suicide cases are reported in Uttar Pradesh at 3.1%.

NCRB reports that there has been a significant percentage increase in suicides[1] in 2020 over 2019 in the following states:- Uttarakhand 82.8%, Mizoram 54.3%, Himachal Pradesh 46.7%, Arunachal Pradesh 42.9%, Assam 36.8% and Jharkhand 30.5%, while highest percentage decrease was reported in Manipur 24.1%, Puducherry 17.2%, Uttar Pradesh 12.1%, Karnataka 8.6%, Haryana 4.5% and Chandigarh 2.3%. Apart from state-wise data, the number of suicides in 53 mega cities show an increasing trend from 2017 to 2020, among which metropolitan cities of India like Delhi, Bengaluru, Chennai, and Mumbai report the highest number of suicidal cases. 34.4% of cases were of persons aged 18-30 years, followed by 31.4% in the 30- 45 year age group. Unlike in the case of women, the NCRB data for Indian men shows a shift in the typical pattern of suicide deaths from 1975-2011. If you look at the findings, the odds of Suicide Death Rates (SDRs) were twice as high in men as in women in 2014, which rose to 2.5 in 2021. For males, the most significant number of suicide deaths occurred among those in the age groups of 18–29 years, 30–44 years and 45–59 years, whereas for females, it is highest at ages 18–29 years[2].

Suicide deaths among men soared by 170.7% from 2014 to 2021 for daily wage earners, reaching an SDR of 34.6 compared with 13.1 of women in 2021. SDR was similarly high for unemployed men (48.2%) and women (27.8%). Suicide deaths fell among women of all educational attainment

levels, while suicide rates among men in all socio-educational levels rose.[2] These figures are observed most prominently in men that studied through class 9–12, demonstrating a 32.6% increase in SDR from 22.6 versus 30.0 in 2014 compared to 2021.[2]

As per NCRB[1], Family Problems account for 33.6% and 'Illness' accounts for 18% of total suicide cases. Among which psychiatric disorders account for a large majority of suicides and suicide attempts; numbers are at least ten times as high as in the general population. Two case-control studies by Vijayakumar L et al. and Gururaj G et al. used psychological autopsy techniques in cities of Chennai and Bangalore, India.[3][4] Among those who died by suicide. Which reports 88% of cases in Chennai and 43% in Bangalore had a diagnosable mental disorder. Depression accounts for 30% of suicidal cases, followed by substance-use-related disorders at 18%, Schizophrenia at 14%, and personality disorders at 13%. The most common methods of suicide in Indian population is Hanging 57.8%, followed by consuming Poison 25.0%, Drowning 5.2%, and Fire/Self-immolation 3.0%. The number of male victims was more than females in all means of suicide except fire/self-immolation.

Individuals who are suicidal are experiencing severe life stressors or mental health disorders that are causing them distress, and suicide is their way to end this distress. However, the existing models of suicide do not explain the development, maintenance and impact of suicide ideation. If suicide ideation is causing individual distress, these models do not explain why they cannot stop this process of continuing to think about suicide. Because suicidal thoughts almost always precede suicide, all aspects of suicidal ideation need to be considered.

Deliberate self-harm. is known by various terms such as Nonfatal suicidal behavior, auto-aggression, focal suicide, self-attack, self-mutilation, symbolic wounding,[1] purposive accidents,[3] parasuicide,[4] self-injurious behavior, which is an intentional act of harming oneself without the intent to die, is a complex behavior associated with various psychological and social factors. DSH in India is eminently 'hidden,unrecognized and silent epidemic' At one year 16% of people repeat self- harm, 0.5-18% die by suicide as found by studies. emphasizing the necessity of awareness and intervention to stop escalating consequences[2][5]

Psychosocial factors, including experiences of domestic violence and family conflict, have been linked to deliberate self-harm, highlighting the broader impact of social environments on this behavior. The distinction between deliberate self-harm and suicide attempts is crucial, as individuals engaging in deliberate self-harm may not always have suicidal intent and may use different methods to harm themselves (Lung et al., 2020). Understanding the functions and correlates of deliberate self-harm is essential for developing effective interventions to prevent self-injury and promote mental well-being.[6][7]

Studies consistently show that deliberate self-harm is more common among females than males, particularly in adolescents and young adults. Females are more likely to engage in self-harm behaviors such as cutting, scratching, and overdosing, while males are more likely to engage in behaviors like hitting, burning, and self-battery.[8]

The interpersonal theory of suicide has mentioned all the factors that lead to desire and later attempt to suicide⁴, but it still doesn't account for the mental process accompanying the decision to commit suicide. Kerkhof and van Spijker (2011) have argued that the experience and process of suicide ideation are similar to worry and rumination. Rumination has been described as a series of connected thoughts about one's own negative feelings and thoughts about the consequences of such feelings (Nolen- Hoeksema, 2004). Worry and rumination have been conceptualised as coping strategies that can have opposite effects on maintaining emotional difficulties, affecting the processes required to develop effective self-regulation. Wells and Matthews (1994, 1996) developed the Self-Regulatory Executive Function (S- REF) model,[9] which suggests that such thinking styles are associated with an individual's metacognitive beliefs. There is some preliminary empirical evidence linking critical concepts of the S-REF model with suicide; Morrison and O'Connor (2008) found in a systematic review that in 10 out of the 11 studies, higher levels of rumination were associated with increased suicide ideation.

In recent years, new studies on suicide have shed some light on the thought process of suicidal patients, in which metacognition is a promising area of interest. Metacognition refers to the stable knowledge or beliefs about one's own cognitive system and knowledge about factors

that affect the functioning of the system, the regulation and awareness of the current state of cognition, and appraisal of the significance of thought and memories (Wells, 1995). [9]

Metacognition consists of both metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive regulation in which, metacognitive knowledge is the information individuals have about their own thinking (including metacognitive beliefs) and knowledge about the strategies affecting thinking. Metacognitive regulation refers to strategies used to change the status of thinking.

It is a higher order thinking which involves active control over one's own thought process. A person with good metacognitive skills and awareness uses these processes to oversee his own learning process, plan and monitor ongoing cognitive activities and compare cognitive outcomes with internal and external standards.[10]

The relationship between metacognition and suicidal ideation has been explored in various contexts, including in individuals with psychosis who are not taking antipsychotic medication, a group known to be at high risk of suicide (Hutton et al., 2018). Understanding metacognitive models of suicidal ideation in different populations is crucial for developing targeted interventions to prevent self-harm and suicide. While interventions like dialectical behavioral therapy have shown effectiveness in reducing self-harm, there is still a need for further research to enhance our understanding of metacognitive beliefs and coping strategies in relation to suicidal behavior (Morken et al., 2019; Yazihan et al., 2019). Over the past decade metacognitive therapy have gained attention in successfully changing the thought process of a person in field of psychiatry helping in various mental illness as well as in learning process. Metacognitive therapy is developed by Adrian Wells in the 1990s, MCT diverges from traditional cognitive therapies by targeting metacognitive beliefs—beliefs about one's own thinking—and the strategies used to regulate thinking. Therapy offers a nuanced and effective approach to treating psychological disorders by targeting metacognitive processes that perpetuate distress. Through techniques that enhance cognitive awareness, modify beliefs, and promote adaptive strategies, MCT equips individuals with tools to manage their thoughts and emotions more effectively[11]

Studies have also investigated the impact of metacognitive beliefs on suicidal ideation, highlighting the importance of exploring these cognitive processes in the context of mental health and suicide prevention (Aadahl et al., 2021). Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and mindfulness-based interventions have been utilized to address suicidal behavior, emphasizing the role of cognitive processes in managing and preventing recurrent suicidal episodes (Williams et al., 2005). Additionally, factors such as self-esteem, interpersonal beliefs, and emotional dysregulation have been identified as contributors to suicidal ideation, underscoring the complex interplay between cognitive, emotional, and social factors in suicidal behaviors (Bhar et al., 2008; Villa et al., 2018; Al-Dajani et al., 2019).

In conclusion, metacognition plays a significant role in shaping cognitive processes, emotional regulation, and social beliefs that influence suicidal behaviors. Understanding the intricate interplay between metacognitive beliefs, cognitive therapies, emotional dysregulation, and environmental stressors is essential for developing effective interventions to prevent suicide and promote mental health.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

John Flavell introduced the term 'metacognition' in the early 1970s based on the word 'metamemory'; Flavell (1979) viewed metacognition as learners' knowledge of their own cognition, defining metacognition as learners' knowledge of their own cognition as 'knowledge and cognition about cognitive phenomena. He used it to refer to an individual's awareness of thinking and learning. "Metacognition refers to one's knowledge concerning one's own cognitive processes and products or anything related to them." [9]

Metacognition was initially used in learning and to develop new strategies for learning in special populations. As it is usually related to learners' knowledge, awareness and control of the processes by which they learn (Brown 1987, Garner and Alexander 1989, Thomas et al.), and the metacognitive learner is thought to be characterised by the ability to recognise, evaluate and, where needed reconstruct existing ideas (Gunstone 1991). Many others followed Flavell's concept of metacognition and came up with a new understanding of the same. Over the past three decades, researchers are interested in the metacognition of various mental health disorders, as it will provide valuable insight to understand the thought process associated with the development and maintenance of disease.

Wells and Matthews (1994, 1996) argued that traditional cognitive models of emotional and psychological disorders neglect factors that modulate and control thinking. They suggested a theoretical framework that conceptualises cognitive processes in the onset and maintenance of emotional disorders. The Self Regulatory Executive Function model (S-REF)[9][11] of psychological disorders (Wells & Matthews, 1994, 1996) is a metacognitive, information processing model. The S-REF model proposes 'cognitive-attentional syndrome (CAS), which consists of heightened self-focus, repetitive and difficult to control negative thinking (worry and rumination), maladaptive coping behaviour and threat monitoring, which contribute to the maintenance of emotional and psychological difficulties. The engagement of the CAS is influenced by metacognition. Metacognition is the information processing element involved in monitoring, interpreting, evaluating and regulating cognition (Flavell, 1979; Wells, 2000). [9][11]

Metacognitive knowledge is information individuals have about their own thinking (including metacognitive beliefs) and knowledge about the strategies affecting thinking. Metacognitive regulation refers to the strategies used to change the status of thinking. Two types of metacognitive beliefs are mainly involved in the development of the psychological disorder. (i) Positive metacognitive beliefs:- is about the effectiveness of the cognitive- attentional syndrome (CAS) process for coping, such as "worrying helps me solve my problems" or rumination helps me better understand my depression.(ii) Negative metacognitive beliefs are about uncontrollability, and negative evaluation of thoughts or feelings like "My worrying is dangerous for me" or "My worrying could make me mad". The Metacognition questionnaire help to assess which domain of metacognition is prominent in the patient during the disease progression. Much evidence has now developed supporting the metacognitive model across a range of emotional and psychological disorders such as depression (Papageorgiou et al. 2009) [12] and anxiety disorders (Sadeghi et al. 2015). OCD (Wells & Papageorgiou, 1998), social anxiety (Gkika & Wells, 2015), post-traumatic stress disorder (Holeva et al., 2001), health anxiety (Melli et al., 2016) and generalised anxiety disorder (well, et al.).

Metacognitive beliefs have also figured prominently in generalised anxiety disorder (GAD) theories. Wells (1995) proposed a metacognitive model of GAD in which, positive and negative metacognitive beliefs about worry are believed to contribute to the development and maintenance of the worry cycle. In support of this model, patients with GAD have been found to endorse stronger negative beliefs about worry. As per C. van der Heiden (2013) , Negative metacognitive beliefs of worrying reflect, negative beliefs about the uncontrollability and dangerousness of worry, eg- "I have no control over my worries" or "Worrying will cause a heart attack". The activation of such negative metacognitions and associated meta-worry is regarded as crucial for the development of GAD. It increases anxiety and worrisome thoughts, leading to counterproductive mental regulation (i.e., thought suppression) and avoidance strategies (i.e., reassurance seeking and keeping away from problematic situations). Negative metacognitive beliefs about worrying will reflect negative beliefs about the uncontrollability and dangerousness

of worry, e.g., “I have no control over my worries” or “Worrying will cause me a heart attack”. The activation of such negative metacognitions and associated meta-worry is crucial for developing GAD. It increases anxiety and worrisome thoughts, leading to counterproductive mental regulation (i.e., thought suppression) and avoidance strategies (i.e., reassurance seeking and keeping away from problematic situations). [12] According to an internet search in Pubmed, Proquest, and other medical literature databases, only two studies are available that explains the role of metacognition in suicidal ideation and attempt. Both studies are done abroad in a limited number of patients with various limitations in the sample.

In a cross-sectional study conducted by Robert I Hallard et al. in 2021, they did a multilevel regression analysis on data from 24 recruited from National Health Sector who had suicidal ideation for two months.[13] The study used Thought Control Questionnaire (TCQ), which measures what people generally do in response to unwanted thoughts (e.g. worry, self-punishment, try to distract, social control and reappraisal). They are measured using a self-reported questionnaire and used metacognitive questionnaire-30 (MCQ-30), which measures (differences in metacognitive beliefs, judgements and monitoring tendencies) together comprise trait level measures. The authors used state-level measures in the study, consisting of the Experience Sampling Methodology (ESM) questionnaire, a set of validated questions from TCQ, Becks scale for suicidal ideation and a response style questionnaire. The study compared the trait-level to state-level measures, demonstrating a significant correlation between the two and suicidal ideation. This study highlighted the importance of the metacognitive process in the maintenance of suicidal ideation. They also found a relationship between three S-REF assumptions and suicidal ideation. (I) The need to control thought is a significant predictor of self-punishment.

3. AIM

To study the relationship between metacognition and suicidal patients.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess metacognition in suicidal patients (Primary Objective)
2. To assess the severity of suicidal intent and hopelessness in suicidal patients (Secondary Objective)

4. MATERIAL AND METHOD

4.1 SOURCE OF DATA:

The study was performed at BLDE (DU) Shri. B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka.

4.2 METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA : By conducting in person interview

4.3 INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patients in the age group of 18-60 years.
2. Self-reported patients with suicidal ideation.
3. Patient with attempted suicide admitted in hospital.
4. Patient referred from other departments who tend to have suicidal ideation.

4.4 EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patient with Schizophrenia or any other psychotic illness.
2. Patient meeting criteria for non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI).
3. If act was initiated during a state of delirium or confusion.
4. If act was undertaken solely for a political or religious objective.

4.5 STUDY DURATION: 18 MONTHS (September 2022- March 2024)

4.6 STUDY TYPE: Observational Cross-Sectional Study

4.7 METHODOLOGY

4.8 SCALS USED FOR ASSESSMENT

- 1) Becks Hopelessness Scale (BHS)
- 2) Becks Suicide Intent Scale (BSIS)
- 3) Metacognition Questionnaire-30 (MCQ-30)
- 4) Becks Depression Inventory- II (BDI II)

4.9 SAMPLING

Sample size

With the anticipated Prevalence of Metacognition in suicide attempt patients 8%, [1] the study would require a sample size of 114 patients with 95% level of confidence and 5% absolute precision

Statistical Analysis:

The data obtained will be entered into a Microsoft Excel sheet, and statistical analysis will be performed using SPSS software.

Data will be expressed as Mean \pm SD or Median and Interquartile range Frequency, percentages and diagrams.

Categorical variables will be compared using Chi-square test. Continuous variables will be analysed for association using spearson

(If necessary) $p < 0.05$ will be considered statistically significant. All statistical tests will perform two-tailed.

4.10 QUANTITATIVE INSTRUMENTS USED

1. BECK HOPELESSNESS SCALE (BHS)

The Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS; Beck et al. 1988) [14] was developed to assess negative attitudes toward one's future and one's perceived inability to avoid negative life events, 20 true/false questions that assess three aspects of hopelessness:- Negative feelings about the future, Loss of motivation, Pessimistic expectations. Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS) is having good test-retest reliability ($r = 0.85$) and good to excellent internal reliability in clinical samples (Kuder Richardson reliabilities ranging from 0.87 to 0.93), Cronbach's alpha for the current sample was 0.92.

2. BECK'S SUICIDE INTENT SCALE (BSI)

The suicide intent scale attempts to redefine the meaning of attempted suicide by categorising it according to presence of intent. Beck's suicide intent scale consists of 20 items, each of which is marked from 1 to 3 points. Beck Scale for Suicidal Ideation (BSI) [15], have good test-retest reliability ($r = 0.88$) and good internal reliability in clinical samples ($\alpha = 0.84$), Cronbach's alpha for the current sample was 0.97.

3. BECK DEPRESSION INVENTORY-II (BDI-II)

The Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II) is a widely used instrument for measuring depression levels. The BDI-II test includes a 21-item, using a four-point scale ranging from 0 (no symptoms) to 3 (extremely severe symptoms). The self-administered test takes about 5 to 10 minutes to complete. Twenty items assess depression symptoms with excellent test-retest reliability ($r = 0.93$) [16] and excellent internal reliability in clinical samples ($\alpha = 0.91$). Cronbach's alpha is 0.92.

4. METACOGNITION QUESTIONNAIRE-30 (MCQ-30)

MCQ-30 is a condensed version of the original MCQ that evaluates individual differences in five factors. MCQ-30 has five subscales: cognitive confidence, positive beliefs about worry, cognitive self-consciousness, negative beliefs about thought uncontrollability and danger, and beliefs about the need to control thoughts. Subscales are calculated by summing the points of associated questions. Subscale scores range from 6 to 24, and total scores range from 30 to 120, with higher scores indicating higher levels of unhelpful metacognitions

Wells and Cartwright-Hatton (2004) reported [11] α ranging from 0.72–0.93 for the various subscales. The five subscales of the MCQ-30 and corresponding α for sample are: (i) positive beliefs about worry (0.79); (ii) negative beliefs concerning uncontrollability and danger (0.81); (iii) cognitive confidence (0.89); (iv) negative beliefs concerning the consequences of not controlling thoughts (0.69); (v) cognitive self-consciousness (0.86).

5. RESULTS

5.1 SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC

1. GENDER DISTRIBUTION:

It was observed that the majority were females, with 68.6 % of patients (67), while 29.4 % of subjects were males (48).

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to Gender

		Frequency	Percent
	Female	67	68.6
	Male	48	29.4
	Total	115	100.0

Graphical representation 1: Gender Distribution

2. AGE DISTRIBUTION:

It was observed that the majority of the patients (%) belonged to the age groups of 40 to 49, followed by (32.7%) belonging to the age group 50 to 60 years. The remaining (22.9%) belonged to the age group 30 to 39 years.

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to age:

		Frequency
Mean-26.7 SD-7.8 Range-18-47	18-30 years	56 Female 31 Male
	31-50 years	11Female 17 Male

Graphical Representation 2 : Age Distribution

3. BACKGROUND

In our study most of the samples were from rural background 72% (98), of lower socio economic status family.

Table 3: Distribution of Socio Economic Class

		Frequency	Percentage
	RURAL	98	72.5
	URBAN	17	25.5
	Total	115	100.0

4. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND:

In both the gender, most of the subjects have done primary or high schooling, followed by most subjects were graduate.

Table 4: Distribution of Educational Qualification

EDUCATION QUALIFICATION				
		Sex		Total
		F	M	
	Illiterate	9	3	12
	Primary /High school	25	26	51
	Higher Secondary	17	8	25
	DEGREE	16	11	27
Total		67	48	115

Graphical Representation 3: Distribution of Educational qualification

5.2 PHENOMENOLOGY OF SUICIDAL IDEATION:

In this study, we observed that most of the subjects were having less duration of suicide ideation, as a result of an acute stressor. Most of the subjects were having suicide ideation of few hours to days, in which % were in group of suicide ideation of less than a day.

Study found out, the main reason for suicide attempts are family or interpersonal issues happened with husband or any close relative of family, followed by financial issues, illness which are chronic, with pessimistic view.

Table 5: Distribution of duration of suicidal ideation

Duration				
< 1 day	<1 month	1 month to 6 Months	>6 months	Total
55	39	11	10	115

Graphical Representation 4: Duration of Suicidal Ideation

Table 6: Reason for Suicide

Reason Suicide Attempt		
	Frequency	Percentage
Family /IPR issue	70	61
Financial Issue	28	24
Illness	9	8
Others (mention some ex)	8	7

Study revealed that, organophosphorus compounds are the main mode of suicide in our study, in which 82% of subjects opted it. Followed by other house hold harmful substances were common.

Table 7: Distribution of mode of suicide attempt

Mode of Suicide Attempt		
	Frequency	Percentage
Organo Phosphorus	95 (52 Female, 43Male)	82
Others (detol, Lizol,phenol, tick powder)	14 (10 Female, 4 Male)	12
Hanging	3 (2 Female, 1 Male)	3
Herbal Products	3 (3Female)	3

5.3 PRE EXISTING PSYCHIATRIC ILLNESS

Out of 115 samples, 82% of samples were not a known case of any psychiatric illness or not were on any psychiatric treatment in past. 18% (8) of the samples were known case of pre-existing depressive disorder and were on or is on active treatment with SSRI before they get admitted in hospital.

Table 8 : pre existing depressive disorder before admission

Pre-existing depressive disorder			
		Frequency	Percentage
	NO	107	82
	YES	8	18
	Total	115	100.0

5.4 INTENT FOR SUICIDE

In the study we used Becks Suicide Intent Scale, which divides the severity of intent into 4 categories, most of the study sample falls in the medium and low intent category with 43% and 39% respectively. Only 2 samples were having high intent for suicide.

Table 9: Severity of suicidal intent in study subjects

		FREQUENCY	PERCENT
BSIS	No Intent	19	16.5
	Low Intent	45	39.1
	Medium Intent	49	42.6
	High Intent	2	1.7
Total		115	100.0

Table 10: Severity of suicide intent to duration of suicidal ideation

BSIS CATEGORY	< 1 DAY	< 1 MONTH	1 MONTH TO 6 MONTH	> 6MONTH	TOTAL
No Intent	10	6	1	2	19
Low Intent	27	11	5	2	45
Medium Intent	18	21	5	5	49
High Intent	0	1	0	1	2

Table 11: Severity of Suicide intent with age

BSIS & AGE				
		18-30	31-50	Total
	No Intent	17	2	19
	Low Intent	30	12	45
	Medium Intent	38	7	49
	High Intent	2	0	2
Total		85	21	115

When it comes to the severity of suicide intent to age, the **data is scattered**, most of the samples were of age group 18-30 years, where the suicide intent was nil to medium intent. **As age advances the suicide attempt were mostly with low intent or medium intent. High intent suicide cases were young in age.**

Table 12: severity of suicide intent with number of attempts

BSIS CATEGORY	S I N G L E A T T E M P T	M U L T I P L E A T T E M P T	N O . C A S E S W I T H A S S O C I A T E D P S Y C H I A T R I C I L L N E S S
No Intent	19	0	2
Low Intent	44	1	1
Medium Intent	46	3	5
High Intent	1	1	0

Table 13: Severity of suicide intent with mode of attempt

BSIS CATEGORY	HANGING	HERBAL PRODUCT	OP POISONING	OTHERS	TOTAL
No Intent	0	0	16	3	19
Low Intent	1	2	36	6	45
Medium Intent	2	1	41	5	49
High Intent	0	0	2	0	2

In the study, most of the samples, attempted suicide using organophosphorus compounds, which consist more than 90% of sample.

When it comes to psychiatric comorbidity (depression) and severity of suicide intent, 5 out of 8 depressive patients were having medium suicide intent. And patients who had multiple suicide attempts were mostly of medium suicide intent.

6 DEPRESSION

Table 14: Distribution of Severity of depression in subjects after the admission using BDI-II

BDI		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Normal	12	10.4
	Mild	32	27.8
	Borderline	30	26.1
	Moderate	32	27.8
	Severe	7	6.1
	Extreme	2	1.7
	Total	115	100.0

All the samples were assessed with Becks Depression inventory II, to look for any severity of depression, which categorize depression into 6 category. Out of 115 samples, 8 samples were

previously diagnosed case of depression, who underwent treatment or who were currently on medication. On Assessing during the interview, majority of samples were having mild to moderate depression. In which mild depression consist of 28% (32), borderline depression was 26% (30), and moderate depression was 28% (32). In the study, minimal number of samples fall in severe (6%) and extreme depression (2%) category.

Graphical Representation 5: Severity of depression with age and gender

Table 15: Distribution of severity of depression with duration of suicide ideation

BDI CATEGORY	<1 DAY	<1 MONTH	1 MONTH TO 6 MONTH	>6MONTH
Normal	3	7	1	1
Mild	20	10	1	1
Borderline	18	8	4	0
Moderate	13	12	3	4
Severe	2	2	2	2
Extreme	0	0	0	2

In the study, most of the samples were having suicidal ideation of less than 1 month, which predominantly in mild to moderate category of depression.

7. HOPELESSNESS

Table 16: Distribution of severity of hopelessness

BHI			
		Frequency	Percent
Valid	None	17	14.8
	Mild	50	43.5
	Moderate	40	34.8
	Severe	8	7.0
	Total	115	100.0

Becks Hopelessness Inventory was used to assess the severity of hopelessness in the study sample, which was categorized into 4, None, Mild, Moderate and Severe.

Among the study sample, 44% (50) of subjects were having mild hopelessness about the future, followed by 35% (40) having moderate hopelessness, and 7% (8) were having severe hopelessness.

Table 17: Distribution of Severity of hopelessness to duration of suicidal ideation

BHI & Duration						
		Duration				Total
		< 1 Day	<1 month	1 Month to 6 Months	>6 months	
BHI	None	10	7	0	0	17
	Mild	28	11	8	3	50
	Moderate	17	18	2	3	40
	Severe	0	3	1	4	8
Total		55	39	11	10	115

In this study when evaluating the hopelessness to duration of suicide ideation, the severity of hopelessness is higher in subjects with less duration of suicide thoughts, and in severe hopelessness is seen as the duration increases.

Table 18 : Distribution of Severity of suicide with number of attempts

BHI CATEGORY	SINGLE ATTEMPT	MULTIPLE ATTEMPT	NO. CASES WITH ASSOCIATED PSYCHIATRIC ILLNESS
None	17	0	01
Mild	48	2	2
Moderate	37	3	3
Severe	8	0	2

8. METACOGNITION

Metacognition of the subjects were assessed using metacognition Questionnaire(MCQ-30), which assess the 5 domains of metacognition. The scores of subjects were analyzed as below, the mean of total score was found to be 61.43 with standard deviation of 9.815.

Table 19 : Metacognition variables

Variable	Mean	Mode	Standard Deviation
MCQ-30	61.43	64	9.815
Lack of Cognitive Confidence	8.48	8	2.276
Positive Belief about worry	9.43	8	3.832
Cognitive self consciousness	9.48	7	3.280
Negative Beliefs about Uncontrollability and Danger	18.29	18	4.093
Need to control thoughts	15.76	17	4.832

In the study, we found that negative beliefs about uncontrollability and danger predominates among all 5 domains in most of the subjects with score of 18.29 and standard deviation of 4.093. followed by need to control thoughts with mean of 15.76.

DISTRIBUTION OF METACOGNITIVE DOMAINS

Table 20: Frequency of Metacognitive domains

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Lack of Cognitive Confidence	1	0.9
Positive Belief about worry	6	5.2
Cognitive self-consciousness	10	8.7
Negative Beliefs about Uncontrollability and Danger	67	58.3
Need to control thoughts	31	27.0

As mentioned above, most of the study samples, were having predominance of metacognition in domains of Negative beliefs about uncontrollability and danger and need to control thoughts, with 58% and 27% respectively.

Table 21: Correlation of metacognition with BDI, BHI, BSIS

MCQ Correlations			MCQ-30	BSIS	BDI	BHI
Spearman's rho	MCQ-30	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.224*	.403**	.398**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.016	.000	.000
	BSIS	Correlation Coefficient	.224*	1.000	.522**	.505**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.016	.	.000	.000
	BDI	Correlation Coefficient	.403**	.522**	1.000	.630**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000
	BHI	Correlation Coefficient	.398**	.505**	.630**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.

On analysis, we found out, metacognition of subjects were positively co-related to the suicide intent, depression and hopelessness with a p value of <0.05.

Table 22 : Correlation of metacognitive domains to BDI, BSIS,BHI

Domains Correlations			BSIS	BDI	BHI	LACK OF CC	PB & W	CSC	NEG B	NEED TO CON
Spearman's rho	BSIS	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.522**	.505**	.090	-.072	.083	.137	.208*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.341	.442	.376	.145	.026
	BDI	Correlation Coefficient	.522**	1.000	.630**	.094	.069	-.008	.396**	.358**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.315	.462	.929	.000	.000
	BHI	Correlation Coefficient	.505**	.630**	1.000	.227*	.129	.159	.299**	.179
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.015	.170	.090	.001	.056
	LACK OF CC	Correlation Coefficient	.090	.094	.227*	1.000	.131	.330**	.113	-.065
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.341	.315	.015	.	.162	.000	.231	.488
	PB & W	Correlation Coefficient	-.072	.069	.129	.131	1.000	.224*	.106	-.187*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.442	.462	.170	.162	.	.016	.260	.045
	CSC	Correlation Coefficient	.083	-.008	.159	.330**	.224*	1.000	-.015	-.148
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.376	.929	.090	.000	.016	.	.873	.113
	NEG B	Correlation Coefficient	.137	.396**	.299**	.113	.106	-.015	1.000	.376**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.145	.000	.001	.231	.260	.873	.	.000
	NEED TO CON	Correlation Coefficient	.208*	.358**	.179	-.065	-.187*	-.148	.376**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.026	.000	.056	.488	.045	.113	.000	.

On analysis suicide intent is negatively associated with positive belief about worry,

Positive association was seen between suicide intent to all other metacognitive domains, with statistical significance to need to control thoughts (p 0.026)

Depression in subjects were positively associated with all metacognitive domains with statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) except cognitive self consciousness (CSC) which is negatively associated.

Severity of Hopelessness in subjects were positively associated with all the metacognitive domains, with statistical significance to lack of cognitive confidence (p 0.015), need to control thoughts (p 0.05) and negative beliefs about worry (p 0.001).

Positive belief about worry was positively associated with cognitive self consciousness (p0.016)

Cognitive self consciousness is positively associated with positive belief about worry (p 0.016)

Need to control thoughts is positively associated with negative belief about worry (p 0.000)

Need to control thoughts is negatively associated with positive belief about worry (p 0.045)

Table 23: Association of MCQ Domain with Duration of Suicide ideation

Duration & Domains						
						Total
		< 1 Day	<1 month	1 month to 6 month	>6 months	
	Lack of Cognitive Confidence	1	0	0	0	1
	Positive Belief about worry	4	2	0	0	6
	Cognitive self consciousness	0	8	0	2	10
	Negative Beliefs about Uncontrollability and Danger	33	17	10	7	67
	Need to control thoughts	17	12	1	1	31
Total		55	39	11	10	115

In our study we observed that, the negative metacognitive domains were predominant in majority of study subjects, in that with the increase in duration of suicidal ideation, the positive belief is less.

The negative beliefs about uncontrollability and danger seems to be predominant though out the duration of suicidal thoughts, with highest among start of the suicidal ideation.

The need to control thoughts is present in subjects during the start of suicidal thoughts and its found less predominant in subjects with longer suicidal ideation.

6. DISCUSSION

115 attempted suicide patients were enrolled in the study, with an age group of 18-50 years, of which the majority were females 67, the mean age of patients was 26.7 years, of rural background.

In our study, we tried to evaluate the patients to understand the metacognitive thoughts and processes they had in their lives prior to a suicide attempt. Metacognition was assessed using metacognitive questionnaire 30, which comprises an equal number of questions to assess five metacognitive domains; along with that, we evaluated the severity of suicidal intent, depression and hopelessness the patient is having towards his future. This made us understand the relationship among each other and, in turn, with metacognition.

As mentioned above, our study comprised more females who have attempted to harm themselves, which accounts for 68% of the sample, which was consistent with the study done by study done by Dr Santosh Ramdurg et al. in 2011 [17] at a tertiary care center, on individuals who attempted suicide and were referred to consultation liaison psychiatry, found out that majority of suicide attempters were young adults aged 18-35 years. This age group is often characterized by significant life transitions, such as entering the workforce, establishing relationships, and gaining independence from family. These transitions can be sources of stress, making young adults particularly vulnerable to mental health issues and suicidal behavior. Moreover, the study revealed a higher incidence of suicide attempts among females. Marital status emerged as another important sociodemographic factor, with a significant proportion of suicide attempters being married. Marital stress, domestic violence, and relationship conflicts can contribute to suicidal behavior. Additionally, the study highlighted that most of the individuals were either unemployed or engaged in unskilled labor. Employment status and job satisfaction are closely linked to mental health, and economic hardships can exacerbate feelings of hopelessness and despair. A high prevalence of psychiatric disorders, particularly depression and anxiety, was noted among the suicide attempters. The study also found that a considerable number of individuals had a history of previous suicide attempts, indicating that a prior attempt is a significant risk factor for future attempts. The methods used for suicide attempts were predominantly poisoning and self-harm.

In our study we observe the shortage of male samples; which was consistent with other studies done by Santosh Ramdurg et al and V. Aadahl A, it may be due to the higher severity of suicidal intent males have compared to females, and the method of suicidal attempt they use may be more lethal. [17][18]

In our study, we observed that the patients of age group 18-30 were more, Several factors contribute to the higher incidence of suicide attempts in this age group are 1. Psychological and Emotional Turmoil, Young adulthood is a critical period for identity formation and self-esteem development. Struggles with self-identity and low self-esteem can lead to feelings of inadequacy and hopelessness. 2. Life Transitions and Stressors which include Educational and Career Pressures, Relationship Challenges, Financial Strain along with this 3. Social and Environmental Factors like Social Isolation, Substance Abuse , Exposure to Trauma and Abuse all add up to the increased suicide tendency in youth.[19][20][21][22][23]

In our study we found out most of the subjects were having family interpersonal issues and financial baggage as prominent reasons for suicide.

Regarding the method used for suicide attempts, our results showed that most of the samples consumed poison to attempt suicide, mainly in females; these results confirm other studies on the role of difference in suicide methods used by males and females for explaining and supporting the “gender paradox” hypothesis. Previous research has shown that men are more likely to use relatively more lethal methods than women.[24]

In contrast, women are more likely to attempt suicide by using poisoning, a technique that allows ample amount of time for intervention by others. Why women choose less lethal means than men has been attributed to several factors, contribute to the tendency for females to choose poisoning as a method for suicide attempts, mainly Perceived Lethality and Accessibility, where Poisoning, often involving household chemicals, medications, or pesticides, is relatively accessible and does not require special tools or physical strength. most of them perceive poisoning as a less violent and less painful method compared to other means, aligning with a desire to avoid

disfigurement and pain. [25][26][27] The use of poison as a mode of suicide also gives them ample amount of time for rescue ability, Poisoning can be seen as a way to communicate distress or a cry for help without a definitive intent to die. This aligns with the higher rates of non-fatal suicide attempts among women, where the intent may be more to express severe emotional pain rather than a determined wish to die.[28][29][30]. In our study, subjects were mainly from families of lower socio-economic status, accounting for 80% of the study population. Other studies have also found that that low SES might play an essential role in predicting suicidal ideation across various age groups. [31][32][33][34]

Regarding the duration of suicidal ideation, most of the subjects were having suicidal ideation of a few hours to a few days with no to medium intent for the act; when we examine the reason for suicide, these subjects tend to have an impulsive act for suicide following interpersonal relationship arguments and acute stressors. Other studies found that females tend to have more impulsive behavior, with low lethal suicide attempts. In our study, we observed that the duration of suicidal ideation and suicide intent are not co-related; most of the subjects tend to have higher suicide intent following an issue, and they attempt suicide, but in the study, the subjects with longer duration of suicidal ideation, tend to be less, which suggest either with the longer the duration the intent of suicide remains constant and low, or subjects with higher suicide intent would have already completed suicide. In other studies done globally, it was found that the intensity of suicidal ideations was found to be the strongest predictor of lethality; those with more intense ideas, in terms of frequency, number of hours per day, and stronger desire to end their lives, may have a direct impact on the technique and lethality of the attempt.[35]

The number of attempts in patients was a strong predictor for future attempts, and in our study, we found out that, out of 5 multiple-attempted subjects, one subject had low intent, three subjects had moderate intent for suicide, and 1 had higher intent. Among these, 3 subjects had a moderate level of depression, and two had extreme depression, with the majority of them having moderate hopelessness and mild hopelessness.

When it comes to depression in the subjects, our study found that 8 subjects were diagnosed case of depression who underwent treatment or are on treatment currently, whereas 12 among the total study population showed depression in assessment scale while 27% of the population had mild depression, 26% had borderline depression, and 27% have a moderate level of depression. Only 6 % of the population had severe depression, with 1.7% having extreme levels of depression. In the study, the age group of 18-30 comprises the highest number of syndromal depression, grading from mild to moderate. When you carefully analyze the subjects with longer duration, the total number of study subjects was less, and the majority of the subjects in the category of longer suicide ideation tend to fall in moderate to extreme levels of depression, which in turn proves the theories proposed in other studies.

Out of the eight known depressive cases, five subjects had multiple attempts, of which three subjects had moderate depression, and two were highly depressed. When you examine the duration of suicide ideation in these subjects, the majority of them had ideation of more than one month, with a few of them having more than six months.

In our study, the hopelessness of subjects about their future was assessed using Beck's hopelessness inventory, which categorized hopelessness into 4, from none to severe. The study revealed that around 46% of subjects had mild hopelessness while 35% had a moderate amount of hopelessness, which constituted the majority of total study subjects. When we look into the severe hopelessness subjects, it's found that 50% of them had suicidal thoughts of more than 6 months duration, while the other 50% had a significantly higher duration of 1-6 months. Multiple studies globally revealed that hopelessness may play a predictive role in suicidal ideation, regardless of changes in depression severity. Many studies in the literature have noticed a link between suicide and hopelessness; it has been established that those who try suicide often have strong feelings of helplessness and hopelessness, and suicide is considered as a solution to the problem. It was found to be significant in females, which was consistent with our study.[36][37][38]

In our study, we aimed at assessing the metacognition of subjects using metacognition questionnaire 30, which help us to evaluate all 5 domains of metacognition, subjects are having. Our study will be one the fewest studies done globally to look into the severity of metacognitive

helplessness and the predominance of a metacognitive domain on a more extensive study sample. Few studies done globally in 2021 assessed the metacognition on limited samples where they tried to look in relation to suicidal ideation, using experience sampling methodology. In our study, we attempted to determine the type of thought process the subject is having by using the metacognition questionnaire 30 to determine which metacognitive domain is predominant; this, in turn, helps us to know more about the type of thought predominant in most of the subjects who attempt suicide.

We found out the mean metacognitive score of subjects was 61.43, which is around more than 50% of the total score; the higher the metacognitive score, the higher the unhelpful metacognition subject has. Metacognition consist of **Positive and negative metacognition**.

Positive metacognition refers to adaptive thoughts and strategies that enhance learning, problem-solving, and emotional well-being. It involves constructive self-reflection and self-regulation that lead to improved cognitive performance and emotional resilience which include Self-Awareness, Strategic Planning, Monitoring and Regulation, Growth Mindset, Reflective Thinking.

Negative metacognition involves maladaptive thoughts and strategies that hinder learning, problem-solving, and emotional well-being. It includes detrimental self-reflection and self-regulation that lead to decreased cognitive performance and increased emotional distress. It include Self-Doubt, Ineffective Strategies, Over-Monitoring, Fixed Mindset, Negative Reflection.

When we analyze the individual domains, out of 5 domains, the majority of subjects, 58% and 27%, had higher scores in Negative Beliefs about Uncontrollability and Danger and the Need to control thoughts, with mean of 18.2 and 15.7, respectively. In contrast, the other three domains were almost equally distributed, with a mean of around 9.

The negative belief about uncontrollability and danger refers to the perception that one's thoughts are beyond control and cannot be managed effectively. Individuals who hold these beliefs often feel powerless over their cognitive processes, leading to a sense of helplessness; on the other hand, it involves the perception that certain thoughts are inherently dangerous and can lead to catastrophic outcomes; this type of belief is characterized by catastrophic thinking, where individuals assume the worst possible consequences from their thoughts.

These beliefs can exacerbate feelings of hopelessness and helplessness, increasing the risk of suicidal behavior. Individuals experiencing suicidal ideation may believe that their distressing thoughts are uncontrollable, which can lead to a pervasive sense of hopelessness, as they feel powerless to stop or manage these thoughts. In contrast, people with suicidal ideation often perceive their emotional pain as overwhelming and impossible. They may believe that their suffering is unbearable and will continue indefinitely, leading to thoughts like, “I can’t endure this pain any longer; it’s too dangerous to continue living.” This belief can drive individuals toward considering suicide as the only escape. Individuals may become hypervigilant about their thoughts and emotions, constantly monitoring for signs of worsening distress or loss of control. This heightened awareness can exacerbate anxiety and reinforce negative beliefs about the uncontrollability and danger of their thoughts. For instance, they might interpret a fleeting thought of suicide as a sign that they are on the brink of a crisis, further entrenching their negative beliefs[39].

These negative metacognitive beliefs can significantly impact mental health, leading to a cycle of increasing distress and suicidal ideation. The perception of uncontrollability fosters helplessness, while the belief in the inherent danger of one’s thoughts amplifies fear and anxiety. This combination can create a feedback loop where individuals feel increasingly trapped by their thoughts and emotions, escalating their risk of suicidal behavior.

Our study found that most of our subjects had negative metacognitive thoughts, especially negative beliefs about uncontrollability and danger, which was consistent throughout our data. This negative metacognition was a predominating factor for the suicidal ideation by creating uncontrollability in stopping the suicidal thoughts which they had about the danger of continuing their negative thoughts about an issue they are facing and making a pessimistic view about the future; when you compare the results with multiple global studies, the data seems to be consistent and going in favor of other studies.

A study done by Morrison and Wells in 2000 compared metacognitive beliefs and processes across different groups, including individuals with hallucinations and panic disorder and a control group without these conditions used. Various self-report questionnaires were used to

assess metacognitive beliefs, including the Metacognitions Questionnaire (MCQ). They found out individuals with hallucinations and panic disorder exhibited significantly higher levels of negative metacognitive beliefs compared to the control group. These beliefs included thoughts about the uncontrollability and danger of their mental processes, and Negative metacognitive beliefs were strongly correlated with emotional distress in both clinical groups. Patients with higher levels of these beliefs experienced more severe symptoms, including anxiety, depression, and hopelessness. The findings suggest that negative metacognitive beliefs contribute to severe emotional distress, which is a known risk factor for suicidal ideation. The heightened levels of distress associated with these beliefs can increase the likelihood of suicidal thoughts and behaviors.[40]

Another study by Papageorgiou & Wells (2001) and Spada, Caselli, & Wells (2012) highlighted how negative metacognitive beliefs about the uncontrollability and danger of rumination are linked to persistent depressive symptoms and hopelessness, both of which are risk factors for suicide.[41][42]

In the context of suicidal ideation, metacognitive beliefs about the need to control thoughts play a significant role. It refers to the conviction that specific thoughts, particularly distressing or suicidal ones, must be tightly regulated and suppressed; individuals may believe that failing to control these thoughts signifies weakness, moral failing, or impending disaster. This can lead to an increased focus on monitoring and attempting to suppress or eliminate unwanted thoughts. The perceived Necessity of Thought Control is when individuals experience suicidal ideation and may feel an urgent need to control their distressing thoughts to prevent harm to themselves or others. They might believe, "If I don't control these thoughts, something terrible will happen," or "I must not think about suicide, or it means I will act on it." This belief can create a paradoxical effect where the more they try to suppress these thoughts, the more persistent and intrusive the thoughts become.

Emotional Distress and Helplessness are the perceived failure to control suicidal thoughts that can lead to intense emotional distress and feelings of helplessness. Individuals may feel trapped in a cycle where their attempts to control their thoughts are unsuccessful, reinforcing the

belief that their situation is hopeless and unmanageable. This can amplify feelings of despair and increase the risk of suicidal behavior.

In our study we found that, the subjects were predominantly having negative metacognition throughout the process of suicidal ideation to attempt, the negative metacognition consist of rumination of thoughts which lead to Hypervigilance. Cognitive load are the efforts to monitor and control thoughts, which can lead to hypervigilance and a significant cognitive load. Individuals may constantly scan their minds for unwanted thoughts, which can be exhausting and increase anxiety. This heightened alertness can further entrench the belief that these thoughts are dangerous and must be controlled at all costs. Similar to negative beliefs about uncontrollability and danger, even the need to control thoughts also contributes to a cycle of increased distress, cognitive overload, and perceived helplessness. The constant effort to control thoughts can exacerbate anxiety and depression, leading to a higher risk of suicidal behavior.[39]

In our study, the lack of cognitive self-confidence was predominant in only one subject, which is a critical component of metacognition is cognitive self-confidence, which refers to the belief in one's ability to think effectively and manage one's cognitive activities. A lack of cognitive self-confidence can lead to various adverse outcomes, including increased anxiety, impaired decision-making, and reduced problem-solving abilities. Cognitive self-confidence involves a positive belief in one's cognitive abilities. It encompasses several aspects: 1) Self-Efficacy in Thinking: The belief that one can effectively engage in and manage cognitive tasks. 2) Trust in Cognitive Processes: Confidence in reasoning, memory, and problem-solving skills. 3) Emotional Regulation: The ability to manage emotions from cognitive tasks, such as anxiety or frustration. [9][40][41][42][43][44][45][46][47][48]

The lack of cognitive self-confidence can manifest as 1) Feelings of Hopelessness and Helplessness. Individuals with low cognitive self-confidence often experience profound feelings of hopelessness and helplessness. They may believe that they are incapable of managing their thoughts and emotions, leading to a sense of being overwhelmed by their mental state. This can significantly contribute to suicidal ideation, as the individual sees no way out of their distress. 2) Increased Anxiety and Rumination: A lack of cognitive self-confidence can lead to heightened

anxiety and rumination. Individuals may constantly doubt their ability to control or understand their thoughts, leading to persistent worry and negative thought cycles. This can exacerbate suicidal thoughts as the individual becomes trapped in a loop of self-doubt and negative self-perception. 3) Impaired Problem-Solving Abilities: When individuals lack confidence in their cognitive abilities, their problem-solving skills suffer. They may feel incapable of solving their problems, leading to increased stress and a sense of futility. [40][41][42][43] This perceived inability to cope with life's challenges can drive individuals toward considering suicide as a way to escape their problems. The lack of cognitive self-confidence can have a profound impact on mental health, particularly suicidal ideation. It can create a vicious cycle where negative thoughts and emotions feed into each other, leading to increasing distress and a perceived lack of control. This can intensify feelings of desperation and make suicide seem like the only viable option. [44][45][46][47][48]

In our study around 5 percent of study subjects had predominant Positive Belief about worry metacognitive thoughts, which refer to the perception that worrying has beneficial effects. These beliefs can include the notion that worrying helps to solve problems, prevents adverse outcomes, or demonstrates care and responsibility. Examples of positive metacognitive beliefs about worry might consist of: "Worrying helps me prepare for the worst.", "If I worry, I'll be able to find a solution." While these beliefs may provide some short-term relief or a sense of control, they can lead to chronic worry and exacerbate mental health issues, including suicidal ideation. Individuals who hold positive beliefs about worry may feel compelled to engage in worrying as a way to prevent suicidal thoughts or manage their emotional state. They might believe they can avoid catastrophic outcomes by worrying about their problems or potential crises. For example, someone might think, "If I keep worrying about my suicidal thoughts, I can prevent them from becoming reality."

Positive beliefs about worry can reinforce negative thought patterns. Individuals who believe worry is beneficial are more likely to ruminate on distressing thoughts. This rumination can intensify feelings of hopelessness and helplessness, which are strongly associated with suicidal

ideation. For instance, worrying excessively about being a burden to others can reinforce the belief that suicide is a viable solution.

Worrying, driven by positive beliefs about its utility, can lead to heightened anxiety and emotional distress. This increased emotional burden can overwhelm an individual's coping mechanisms, pushing them closer to suicidal thoughts and behaviors. The chronic stress of constant worry can also lead to mental and physical exhaustion, reducing an individual's resilience against suicidal ideation.

Positive beliefs about worry can have a profound impact on mental health. These beliefs can create a cycle where worry leads to increased anxiety, reinforcing the need to worry even more. This cycle can contribute to the development and maintenance of anxiety disorders, depression, and suicidal ideation. The belief that worry is beneficial can prevent individuals from seeking healthier coping mechanisms, trapping them in a state of chronic distress.

Multiple studies reported that These beliefs, although seemingly helpful, can paradoxically contribute to the persistence of worry and anxiety, which can exacerbate mental health issues, including depression and suicidal ideation.[41][42]

Our study was one of the fewest studies done globally to evaluate the relationship of metacognition with hopelessness, depression and suicide intent. In our research, we used Spearman's rho association between the MCQ-30, BHI, BDI, and BSIS. We found out all 4 components were significantly positively correlated with one another, with a statistical significance of $p < 0.05$. In studies done globally, Negative metacognitive beliefs and processes, such as excessive worry, rumination, and a perceived lack of control over thoughts, can exacerbate psychological distress and contribute to the development and intensification of suicidal intent. A study by O'Connor and Nock in 2014 emphasizes that individuals who struggle with cognitive and emotional regulation are at higher risk for suicidal behavior. Negative metacognitive beliefs about one's inability to manage distressing thoughts and emotions play a significant role in this dysregulation. [49]

In study done by Spada, M. M., & Wells, A. (2006). "Metacognitive Beliefs and Emotional Dysregulation in Depression and Anxiety" It finds that individuals with depression who hold

negative metacognitive beliefs about their thoughts and emotions are more likely to experience severe emotional dysregulation, which is closely linked to increased suicidal ideation [40]. Likewise, in the study Fisher, P. L., & Wells, A. (2009). "Metacognitive Therapy for Recurrent and Persistent Depression: A Multiple-Baseline Study" This study evaluates the effectiveness of MCT in treating recurrent and persistent depression, showing significant reductions in both depressive symptoms and suicidal ideation. The therapy's focus on altering metacognitive beliefs about thoughts and emotions helped decrease the severity and frequency of suicidal thoughts,[42] which in turn signifies that metacognitive thinking, especially the negative metacognitive thought process, is interlinked with depression and suicidal ideation.

In study done by Cieslak, R., & Nolen-Hoeksema, S. (2006). In "Rumination, Cognitive Vulnerability, and Depressive Symptoms," he found that individuals with high levels of rumination and negative metacognitive beliefs are more likely to experience persistent feelings of hopelessness.

In our study, when we analyze the co-relation of each metacognitive domain to the severity of suicide intent, depression and hopelessness, we found out that the severity of subjects' suicide intent is negatively associated with the optimistic belief about worry but positively associated with negative metacognitive domains, mainly with the need to control thoughts and negative beliefs about worry, where the statistical significance was established with the need to control thoughts (p 0.026). When analyzing the co-relation severity of depression to metacognitive domains, we see a statistically significant correlation between the need to control thoughts (p 0.00) and negative beliefs about worry (p 0.00) and a negative correlation with cognitive self-consciousness.

About the severity of hopelessness to metacognitive domains, we found a positive correlation between the lack of cognitive confidence (p 0.015), need to control thoughts (p 0.056) and Negative Beliefs about Uncontrollability and Danger (p 0.001). All these findings of this study were consistent with multiple studies done on metacognition in suicide.[13][18]

In a cross-sectional study conducted by Robert I Hallard et al. in 2021[13], they did a multilevel regression analysis on data from 24 recruited from the National Health Sector who had suicidal ideation for two months, where they aimed to test the hypothesis firstly that metacognitive beliefs

about the need to control thoughts, the benefits of worry and the uncontrollability and dangerousness of worry would predict the use of worry- and punishment-related thought control strategies, secondly worry- and punishment-related thought control strategy use, alongside rumination, would predict suicidal ideation and finally use of adaptive thought control strategies (distraction, social control and reappraisal) would negatively predict suicidal ideation.

Results showed that beliefs about the need to control thoughts predicted self-punishment, worry, rumination and suicidal ideation. Adaptive thought control strategies were negatively associated with suicidal ideation, with distraction being the most significant independent negative predictor. Maladaptive thought control strategies are as important in the development of suicidal ideation as rumination, and metacognitive beliefs should be considered in suicidal samples.

7. LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

1. The sample we obtained is from subjects who were admitted to the hospital following the attempt of suicide, which lacks the diversity of community subject inclusion.
2. Due to fear of medicolegal complications, many of the subjects were showing a tendency to hide crucial information regarding the suicidal attempt.
3. Subjects inhibition or loss of memory in giving details about the thought process they had before suicidal act.
4. The study sample consisted more of attempted suicide by poison, which restricts the study from understanding the thought process in subjects who used more lethal ways of suicide.

8. STRENGTH OF THE STUDY

1. With very few studies done globally, this study would be one of the first studies done to understand the metacognitive process associated with suicide in India.
2. Most of the studies done globally had a very small sample size, but our study was successfully done on a larger sample from the southern part of India.
3. Understanding the metacognitive process of suicide would give us a better understanding of suicide and in turn help in formulating metacognitive therapy which will help in preventing lives.

9. CONCLUSION

Metacognition plays a significant role in shaping cognitive processes, emotional regulation, and social beliefs that influence suicidal behaviors. Understanding the intricate interplay between metacognitive beliefs, cognitive therapies, emotional dysregulation, and environmental stressors is essential for developing effective interventions to prevent suicide and promote mental health. From this study we could conclude that, the negative metacognition is the prominent metacognitive thought that influence a person's thought process by rumination and in turn worsening the depression, heightening the hopelessness and in turn strengthening the suicide intent they have. Understanding metacognitive models of suicidal ideation in different populations is crucial for developing targeted interventions to prevent self-harm and suicide.

10. SUMMARY

1. The study enrolled 115 attempted suicide patients aged 18-50, with a mean age of 26.7 years, primarily females (67 out of 115).
2. The focus was on evaluating the patients' metacognitive thoughts and processes before their suicide attempts, assessed using the Metacognitive Questionnaire 30 (MCQ-30).
3. The study also evaluated the severity of suicidal intent, depression, and hopelessness to understand their relationships with metacognition and its domains
4. Majority of participants were young adults (18-30 years) and females, consistent with previous studies.
5. Factors like interpersonal and financial issues were the reason for majority of subjects to have thoughts about suicide
6. Consuming poisoning was the most common method, especially among females.
7. The study observed most of the subjects had a shorter duration of suicidal ideation before attempts, often impulsive following interpersonal conflicts.
8. Longer durations of suicidal ideation were associated with moderate to extreme depression levels.
9. A significant proportion of subjects had depression, with varying severity.
10. Hopelessness was prevalent, with a majority showing mild to moderate levels.
11. Severe hopelessness was linked to prolonged suicidal ideation.
12. The mean metacognitive score was 61.43, indicating high unhelpful metacognition.
13. Negative beliefs about uncontrollability and danger, and the need to control thoughts, were predominant.
14. Negative metacognition was strongly linked to suicidal ideation, hopelessness, and depression.
15. Suicide Intent was Positively correlated with negative metacognitive domains, especially the need to control thoughts.

16. Depression was Strongly correlated with the need to control thoughts and negative beliefs about worry.
17. Hopelessness was Positively correlated with the lack of cognitive confidence and negative beliefs about uncontrollability and danger.
18. The findings are consistent with multiple global studies linking metacognitive beliefs and processes with increased suicidal ideation and behavior.
19. Study emphasize the role of negative metacognitive beliefs in emotional dysregulation and distress.
20. The study highlights the critical role of negative metacognitive thoughts in suicidal behavior.
21. Addressing these metacognitive beliefs through therapeutic interventions could help reduce suicidal ideation and attempts

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12.ANNEXURE-I

BLDE

(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)

Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956

Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA
BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 657/2022-23 30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on **Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology** scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "ASSESSMENT OF METACOGNITION IN SUICIDAL PATIENTS:- A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr. SREERAG ASHOK

NAME OF THE GUIDE: Dr. S.P CHAUKIMATH, Professor & HoD, Dept. of Psychiatry.

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura

Dr. Akram A. Naikwadi
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutinization.

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.

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ANNEXURE –II

B.L.D.E. (DU), SHRI B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL & RC

VIJAYAPURA - 586103

INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN

DISSERTATION/RESEARCH

I, the undersigned, _____, S/O D/O W/O _____, aged _____ years, ordinarily resident of _____ do hereby state/declare that Dr. SREERAG ASHOK of Shri. B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre have explained to me in my own language that he is conducting a dissertation/research titled “ASSESSMENT OF METACOGNITION IN SUICIDAL PATIENT” under the guidance of Dr S.P Chaukimath & Dr Santosh Ramdurg, and requesting my participation in the study. Apart from routine treatment procedures, follow-up observations will be utilized for the study as reference data. Further Doctor has informed me that my participation in this study helped in the evaluation of the results of the study, which is a useful reference for the treatment of other similar cases in the near future. The Doctor has also informed me that information given by me, observations made photographs, and video graphs taken upon me by the investigator will be kept confidential and not assessed by a person other than my legal hirer or me except for academic purposes.

The Doctor informed me that though my participation is purely voluntary, based on the information given by me, I can ask for any clarification during the course of treatment/study related to diagnosis, procedure of treatment, the result of treatment or prognosis.

At the same time, I have been informed that I can withdraw from my participation in this study at any time if I want, or the investigator can terminate me from the study at any time from the study but not the procedure of treatment and follow-up unless I request to be discharged.

After understanding the nature of dissertation or research, diagnosis made, mode of treatment, I the undersigned Shri/Smt _____ under my full conscious state of mind agree to participate in the said research/dissertation.

Signature of the patient:

Signature of Doctor:

Dr SREERAG ASHOK

Witness: 1.

ANNEXURE- III

PROFOMA FOR GENERAL DETAILS COLLECTION

BLDE'S SHRI B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL & RC, VIJAYAPURA.

Name:

CASE NO:

Age:

IP NO:

Sex:

D.O.A:

Religion:

Duration of Admission:

Occupation:

D.O.D:

Residence: Urban / Rural

Family income:

Address and Mobile number:

Educational status: No schooling, 1-5 class, 5-10 class, 11-12 class, Degree, Post

Degree

Socio-Economic status: L-SES / M-SES / U-SES

Details of Illness

Diagnosed with any Psychiatric illness in past- YES / NO

Any History of Psychiatric illness / Suicide in Family -

Duration of suicidal ideation -

Any acute stressor present- YES / NO

Stressor - Family issue/ Financial / IPR issue / Illness / Others

Any Treatment sought previously- Medical / Psychological / Traditional / Religious / Faith

Healing Techniques / internet search based

Did any treatment found helpful- Yes / No (Details if yes)

Beck Hopelessness Scale

Instructions:

This questionnaire consists of 20 statements. Please read the statements carefully one by one. If the statement describes your attitude for the past week including today, darken the circle with a 'T' indicating TRUE in the column next to the statement. If the statement does not describe your attitude, darken the circle with an 'F' indicating FALSE in the column next to this statement. Please be sure to read each statement carefully.

I look forward to the future with hope and enthusiasm	(T)	(F)
I might as well give up because there is nothing I can do about making things better for myself	(T)	(F)
When things are going badly, I am helped by knowing that they cannot stay that way forever	(T)	(F)
I can't imagine what my life would be in 10 years	(T)	(F)
I have enough time to accomplish the things I want to do	(T)	(F)
In the future, I expect to succeed in what concerns me most	(T)	(F)
My future seems dark to me	(T)	(F)
I happen to be particularly lucky, and I expect to get more of the good things in life than the average person	(T)	(F)
I just can't get the breaks, and there's no reason I will in the future	(T)	(F)
My past experiences have prepared me well for the future	(T)	(F)
All I can see ahead of me is unpleasantness, rather than pleasantness	(T)	(F)
I don't expect to get what I really want	(T)	(F)
When I look ahead in the future, I expect to be happier than I am now	(T)	(F)
Things just don't work out the way I want them to	(T)	(F)
I have great faith in the future	(T)	(F)
I never get what I want, so its foolish to want anything	(T)	(F)
Its very unlikely that I will get any real satisfaction in the future	(T)	(F)
The future seems vague and uncertain to me	(T)	(F)
I can look forward to more good times than bad times	(T)	(F)

BECK'S SUICIDE INTENT SCALE

1. Isolation
 - a. Somebody present
 - b. Somebody nearby, or in visual or vocal contact
 - c. No one nearby or in visual or vocal contact
2. Timing
 - a. Intervention is probable
 - b. Intervention is not likely
 - c. Intervention is highly unlikely
3. Precautions against discovery/intervention
 - a. No precautions
 - b. Passive precautions (as avoiding other but doing nothing to prevent their intervention; alone in room with unlocked door)
 - c. Active precautions (as locked door)
4. Acting to get help during/after attempt
 - a. Notified potential helper regarding attempt
 - b. Contacted but did not specifically notify potential helper regarding attempt
 - c. Did not contact or notify potential helper
5. Final acts in anticipation of death (will, gifts, insurance)
 - a. None
 - b. Thought about or made some arrangements
 - c. Made definite plans or completed arrangements
6. Active preparation for attempt
 - a. None
 - b. Minimal to moderate
 - c. Extensive
7. Suicide Note
 - a. Absence of note
 - b. Note written, but torn up; note thought about
 - c. Presence of note
8. Overt communication of intent before the attempt
 - a. None
 - b. Equivocal communication
 - c. Unequivocal communication

Self Report

9. Alleged purpose of attempt
 - a. To manipulate environment, get attention, get revenge
 - b. Components of above and below
 - c. To escape, surcease, solve problems
 - d.

10. Expectations of fatality
 - a. Thought that death was unlikely
 - b. Thought that death was possible but not probable
 - c. Thought that death was probable or certain
11. Conception of method's lethality
 - a. Did less to self than s/he thought would be lethal
 - b. Wasn't sure if what s/he did would be lethal
 - c. Equaled or exceeded what s/he thought would be lethal
12. Seriousness of attempt
 - a. Did no seriously attempt to end life
 - b. Uncertain about seriousness to end life
 - c. Seriously attempted to end life
13. Attitude toward living/dying
 - a. Did not want to die
 - b. Components of above and below
 - c. Wanted to die
14. Conception of medical rescuability
 - a. Thought that death would be unlikely if he received medical attention
 - b. Was uncertain whether death could be averted by medical attention
 - c. Was certain of death even if he received medical attention
15. Degree of premeditation
 - a. None; impulsive
 - b. Suicide contemplated for three hours or less prior to attempt
 - c. Suicide contemplated for more than three hours prior to attempt
 - d. *Other Aspects (Not included in total score)*
16. Reaction to attempt
 - a. Sorry it was made; feels foolish; ashamed
 - b. Accepts both attempt and failure
 - c. Regrets failure of attempt
17. Visualization of death
 - a. Life after death, reunion with descendants
 - b. Never-ending sleep, darkness, end of things
 - c. No conceptions of or thoughts about death
18. Number of previous attempts
 - a. None
 - b. One or two
 - c. Three or more
 - d.

19. Relationship between alcohol intake and attempt

- a. Some alcohol intake prior to but not related to attempt; reportedly not enough to impair judgment, reality testing
- b. Enough alcohol intake to impair judgment; reality testing and diminish responsibility
- c. Intentional intake of alcohol in order to facilitate implementation of attempt

20. Relationship between drug intake and attempt

- a. Some drug intake prior to but not related to attempt; reportedly not enough to impair judgment, reality testing
- b. Enough drug intake to impair judgment; reality testing and diminish responsibility
- c. Intentional intake of drug in order to facilitate implementation of attempt

15-19 Low Intent
20-28 Medium Intent
29+ High Intent

There is also a greater risk of repeated attempts the higher the intent rating.

Beck's Depression Inventory

This depression inventory can be self-scored. The scoring scale is at the end of the questionnaire.

1.
 - 0 I do not feel sad.
 - 1 I feel sad
 - 2 I am sad all the time and I can't snap out of it.
 - 3 I am so sad and unhappy that I can't stand it.
2.
 - 0 I am not particularly discouraged about the future.
 - 1 I feel discouraged about the future.
 - 2 I feel I have nothing to look forward to.
 - 3 I feel the future is hopeless and that things cannot improve.
3.
 - 0 I do not feel like a failure.
 - 1 I feel I have failed more than the average person.
 - 2 As I look back on my life, all I can see is a lot of failures.
 - 3 I feel I am a complete failure as a person.
4.
 - 0 I get as much satisfaction out of things as I used to.
 - 1 I don't enjoy things the way I used to.
 - 2 I don't get real satisfaction out of anything anymore.
 - 3 I am dissatisfied or bored with everything.
5.
 - 0 I don't feel particularly guilty
 - 1 I feel guilty a good part of the time.
 - 2 I feel quite guilty most of the time.
 - 3 I feel guilty all of the time.
6.
 - 0 I don't feel I am being punished.
 - 1 I feel I may be punished.
 - 2 I expect to be punished.
 - 3 I feel I am being punished.
7.
 - 0 I don't feel disappointed in myself.
 - 1 I am disappointed in myself.
 - 2 I am disgusted with myself.
 - 3 I hate myself.
8.
 - 0 I don't feel I am any worse than anybody else.
 - 1 I am critical of myself for my weaknesses or mistakes.
 - 2 I blame myself all the time for my faults.
 - 3 I blame myself for everything bad that happens.
9.
 - 0 I don't have any thoughts of killing myself.
 - 1 I have thoughts of killing myself, but I would not carry them out.
 - 2 I would like to kill myself.
 - 3 I would kill myself if I had the chance.
10.
 - 0 I don't cry any more than usual.
 - 1 I cry more now than I used to.
 - 2 I cry all the time now.
 - 3 I used to be able to cry, but now I can't cry even though I want to.

11.
0 I am no more irritated by things than I ever was.
1 I am slightly more irritated now than usual.
2 I am quite annoyed or irritated a good deal of the time.
3 I feel irritated all the time.
12.
0 I have not lost interest in other people.
1 I am less interested in other people than I used to be.
2 I have lost most of my interest in other people.
3 I have lost all of my interest in other people.
13.
0 I make decisions about as well as I ever could.
1 I put off making decisions more than I used to.
2 I have greater difficulty in making decisions more than I used to.
3 I can't make decisions at all anymore.
14.
0 I don't feel that I look any worse than I used to.
1 I am worried that I am looking old or unattractive.
2 I feel there are permanent changes in my appearance that make me look unattractive
3 I believe that I look ugly.
15.
0 I can work about as well as before.
1 It takes an extra effort to get started at doing something.
2 I have to push myself very hard to do anything.
3 I can't do any work at all.
16.
0 I can sleep as well as usual.
1 I don't sleep as well as I used to.
2 I wake up 1-2 hours earlier than usual and find it hard to get back to sleep.
3 I wake up several hours earlier than I used to and cannot get back to sleep.
17.
0 I don't get more tired than usual.
1 I get tired more easily than I used to.
2 I get tired from doing almost anything.
3 I am too tired to do anything.
18.
0 My appetite is no worse than usual.
1 My appetite is not as good as it used to be.
2 My appetite is much worse now.
3 I have no appetite at all anymore.
19.
0 I haven't lost much weight, if any, lately.
1 I have lost more than five pounds.
2 I have lost more than ten pounds.
3 I have lost more than fifteen pounds.

- 20.
- 0 I am no more worried about my health than usual.
 - 1 I am worried about physical problems like aches, pains, upset stomach, or constipation.
 - 2 I am very worried about physical problems and it's hard to think of much else.
 - 3 I am so worried about my physical problems that I cannot think of anything else.
- 21.
- 0 I have not noticed any recent change in my interest in sex.
 - 1 I am less interested in sex than I used to be.
 - 2 I have almost no interest in sex.
 - 3 I have lost interest in sex completely.

INTERPRETING THE BECK DEPRESSION INVENTORY

Now that you have completed the questionnaire, add up the score for each of the twenty-one questions by counting the number to the right of each question you marked. The highest possible total for the whole test would be sixty-three. This would mean you circled number three on all twenty-one questions. Since the lowest possible score for each question is zero, the lowest possible score for the test would be zero. This would mean you circles zero on each question. You can evaluate your depression according to the Table below.

Total Score	Levels of Depression
1-10	These ups and downs are considered normal
11-16	Mild mood disturbance
17-20	Borderline clinical depression
21-30	Moderate depression
31-40	Severe depression
over 40	Extreme depression

A PERSISTENT SCORE OF 17 OR ABOVE INDICATES THAT YOU MAY NEED MEDICAL TREATMENT. IF YOU HAVE ANY CARDIAC CONCERNS, PLEASE CONTACT CARDIOVASCULAR INTERVENTIONS, P.A. at 407-894-4880

Metacognitions questionnaire-30 (MCQ-30)

1= Do not agree, 2= Agree slightly, 3 = Agree moderately, 4=Agree very much

1. Worrying helps me to avoid problems in the future
2. My worrying is dangerous for me
3. I think a lot about my thoughts
4. I could make myself sick with worrying
5. I am aware of the way my mind works when I am thinking through a problem
6. If I did not control a worrying thought, and then it happened, it would be my fault.
7. I need to worry in order to remain organised.
8. I have little confidence in my memory for words and names
9. My worrying thoughts persist, no matter how I try to stop them.
10. Worrying helps me to get things sorted out in my mind
11. I cannot ignore my worrying thoughts.
12. I monitor my thoughts
13. I should be in control of my thoughts all of the time.
14. My memory can mislead me at times
15. My worrying could make me go mad
16. I am constantly aware of my thinking
17. I have a poor memory
18. I pay close attention to the way my mind works
19. Worrying helps me cope
20. Not being able to control my thoughts is a sign of weakness
21. When I start worrying I cannot stop
22. I will be punished for not controlling certain thoughts
23. Worrying helps me to solve problems.
24. I have little confidence in my memory for places
25. It is bad to think certain thoughts.
26. I do not trust my memory
27. If I could not control my thoughts, I would not be able to function
28. I need to worry, in order to work well.
29. I have little confidence in my memory for actions
30. I constantly examine my thoughts

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Publications : 14

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P.G Guide : 4 YEARS

U.G teacher : 8 YEARS 10 MONTHS

Publications: 22 published article in international, national and state journals

Research projects: 6 projects are ongoing

BIO-DATA

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